

Working Group Business Models & Sustainability

DIHNET.EU aims at developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), DIH networks and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The DIHNET Working Groups (WG) will identify and target challenges that require the input from the DIH community and the different stakeholders in four main topics: “Finance and funding opportunities”, “Collaboration activities and mechanisms”, “Connection with policies and strategies” and “Business Models and Sustainability”.

Objectives

The objective of the Working Group on “Business Models and Sustainability” is to address the challenges to ensure effective and sustainable collaboration among the DIHs in Europe and explore possibilities for business models that can support this collaboration and effective network.

Special attention will be paid to identify the possible constraints and obstacles in the setting-up of European collaboration between DIHs and to define relevant actions to overcome such challenges.

What are the challenges?

- To identify the prerequisites of successful pan-European collaborations.
- To identify the added value of collaborating and participating in a network (why is a pan-European network important and needed)
- To identify possible business models for collaboration in a network.
- To jointly develop a common understanding and plan for future participation and development in pan-EU collaboration activities.

How the DIH community is going to address these challenges will be discussed in the working group.

How to get engaged with the WG

You can join the DIHNET.EU Community platform at www.dihnet.eu or contact the WG coordinator.

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DIHNET.EU
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